

Ben@Rail

Deliverable D 4.2

Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Knowledge Transfer of the Project's Results

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1. Executive Summary

The aim of this document is to provide a strategy for the dissemination, exploitation, and knowledge transfer of the Ben@Rail project results, and to describe the tools that will be used to facilitate the spread of information and knowledge from the results created by the project, among and beyond the members of the consortium and beyond the life of the project.

For the dissemination of Ben@Rail to be successful, there needs to be a good cooperation between all the members of the consortium throughout the life of the project.

In this respect, an overview of the dissemination and communication activities to be undertaken during the project's life is going to be provided.

The ambition of Ben@Rail is to analyse the contents of Europe's Rails Master Plan in light of the end-users' expectations for clear societal cases, and thus becoming the reference point for the development of the assessment of EU-funded projects vis-a-vis users' and stakeholders' needs and requirements.

Through this, Ben@Rail will serve as a source of data and recommendations supporting writing of the Multi-Annual Action Plan and evaluating the ER JU Master Plan. The results of Ben@Rail will be used for the promotion of Shift2Rail and Europe's Rail to widen their audience and to raise awareness on the effects of EU-funded R&I activities on the Railway stakeholders and users.

The close link between Ben@Rail and the Shift2Rail JU, ERRAC and its complementary EU project IMPACT-2 will ensure further dissemination of the results achieved by the project.

This deliverable is a dynamic document evolving with the project and it will be complemented in M9 by D4.3 "Summary of dissemination and exploitation activities".

2. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
CCA	Cross-Cutting Activities
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
ERRAC	European Rail Research Advisory Board
ERJU	Europe's Rail Joint Undertaking
ETP	European Technology Platform
IP	Innovation Programme
MAAP	Multi-Annual Action Plan
S2RJU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking

3. Background

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D4.2 “Plan for the dissemination, exploitation, and knowledge transfer of the project’s results” in the framework of WP4, Task 4.3.

4. Objective/Aim

This document has been prepared to provide a definition of the target audience and the strategy and activities for the successful dissemination, exploitation, and knowledge transfer of Ben@Rail results, in alignment with Shift2Rail’s communication and dissemination strategy. This deliverable is a dynamic document evolving with the project and it will be complemented in M9 by D4.3 “Summary of dissemination and exploitation activities”.

The objective of the dissemination is to use the results of Ben@Rail to promote Shift2Rail results to widen its audience.

In this report, materials and strategies for communicating and disseminating Ben@Rail and Shift2Rail to railway stakeholders, railway operators and infrastructure managers, the scientific community, the EU-representatives and the general public are presented. These include:

- the creation of a project graphic identity;
- the creation of a public webpage;
- the creation of a digital project flyer;
- the participation in ERRAC events;
- the submission of one scientific publication;
- the production of one animated presentation or video to present the results of the project, following the communication guidelines of ERRAC Working Group 3 (communication);
- the collaboration with Shift2Rail, ERRAC and project S2R-CFM-CCA-01-2017 (IMPACT-2);
- the elaboration of a comprehensive document based on key findings and recommendations of Ben@Rail: D3.1 Top-down analysis of the railway stakeholders’ masterplan goals.

Throughout the project, the “Administrative management, technical coordination and dissemination” work package (WP4) will drive the dissemination of information, particularly for the purpose of ensuring future exploitation and the collaboration with Shift2Rail, ERRAC and other Shift2Rail projects as mentioned above.

5. Definitions and target groups

Throughout this document, the terms “communication”, “dissemination” and “exploitation” are frequently used. The definitions used by the authors are shown below:

- **Communication:** the aim of taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.
- **Dissemination:** the aim of dissemination is to spread the outputs of the project among interested parties. This activity involves presentation of the project’s results to the European railway community and the industrial and scientific community, while managing knowledge within the consortium. The means to achieve this are described in this document.
- **Exploitation:** the aim of exploitation is to favour the market uptake through the use of the results of the project, particularly by using them in further research activities (outside the action of Ben@Rail). This activity involves the use of the project’s results and developed methodologies by stakeholders and end users.

The consortium plans to disseminate the results at different levels, with the main target audience listed below:

- Shift2Rail and its successor Europe’s Rail Joint Undertakings;
- Scientific Communities, European Technology Platforms;
- Railway Undertakings, Infrastructure Managers and train operators;
- Industrial Transport Associations;
- Associations, regulatory and standardisation bodies;
- National, European and international authorities;
- Past and ongoing projects.

6. Dissemination plan

6.1 Objectives

Dissemination will focus on two objectives during the project implementation.

- Communication activities aiming at informing the relevant stakeholders about the main activities and results achieved during the nine months of Ben@Rail;
- Engagement with rail stakeholders through workshops aiming at gathering inputs on stakeholders' requirements, particularly relevant for WP1.

External communication and dissemination will be achieved by creating a project identity and a public website, attending conferences and relevant events and publishing one scientific article in academic journals or conference.

As outlined in the Ben@Rail description of work, the dissemination objectives are to:

- Develop dissemination activities to facilitate wide-spread information of the project and its results;
- Set up communication channels and activities in collaboration with the Shift2Rail JU;
- Ensure that the project outputs reach all relevant stakeholders;
- Liaise and foster close collaboration with ERRAC, the Deutsche Zentrum für Schienenverkehrsforschung and rail passengers/freight associations.

6.2 Dissemination measures

6.2.1 Project identity

A project identity has been created at the beginning of the project including templates for presentations and reports as well as the Ben@Rail logo and design guidelines. The project identity will help dissemination activities and ensure a consistent communication of the project concept, objectives and results.

LOGO

The Logo of the project was made by EURNEX. This logo should be present on all communication materials produced for the project.

The Logo should be represented as it is in a whole, but the image and the name may also be used separately as seen on the cover of this guide. For all separate use, please consult EURNEX before. The logo should be used in colour as far as it is possible but can also be used in black and white version when necessary.

COLOURS & TYPOGRAPHY

The Font used for the Logo is BELLOTA italic. It's a free font downloadable from Google Fonts:
<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Bellota>

The font used for texts in official document should be a sans serif, like the: Open sans light.

All dissemination of results in any form, must display the JU logo, the EU emblem and include the following text:

Ben@Rail

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101046258."

Figure 1. Ben@Rail design identity

6.2.2 Webpage

A webpage dedicated to Ben@Rail has been integrated within the EURNEX website at the beginning of the project. The webpage (<https://www.eurnex.org/benatrail/>) is publicly accessible and is updated on a regular basis. It contains general information regarding the structure, objectives, and progress of the project. All relevant public deliverables will be published on the website together with a publishable summary.

Figure 2. Ben@Rail webpage

6.2.3 Digital flyer

During the first months of the project, a digital flyer has been created. The main objective of this publication is to provide the wide audience with some preliminary information on the goals of the project, the structure and main planned activities and the members of the Ben@Rail consortium. The public flyer is available on the Ben@Rail webpage.

Ben@Rail

Ben@Rail is a 9 month project, funded by Shift2Rail JU under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme within the Cross-Cutting Activities (CCA). Ben@Rail represents the bridge between Work Area 1 "Socio-economics and System Platform Demonstrators" and Work Area 2 "Key Performance Indicators". Ben@Rail contributes to the success of the future Europe's Rail Joint Undertaking by applying a scientifically proven methodology to quantify the efficacy of EU-funded R&I activities.

Partners: EURNEX (Coordinator), RWTH Aachen University, KTH royal institute of technology

Supported by: Shift2Rail JU Advisory group will include ERRAC Steering Committee and the German Centre for Rail Transport Research.

Budget: 169 985.00€

Duration: 9 months
1st September 2021 – 31st May 2022

The main objective of Ben@Rail is to strengthen the effectiveness of EU-funded R&I activities in the railway research domain amongst the rail sector stakeholders, in order to ensure a tight adherence of the innovations stemming from Europe's Rail Joint Undertaking (ERJU) and its Master Plan to the needs of railway stakeholders and final users.

To reach this objective, Ben@Rail will provide evidence-based research to assess the extent to which the foreseen innovations of Shift2Rail and its successor respond to clear societal cases and stakeholders' and users' expectations.

In particular, Ben@Rail aims at developing a top-down analysis of the railway stakeholders' masterplan goals, indicating whether the technological and general concepts that are supposed to be developed by Europe's Rail-funded projects meet the stakeholders' expectations.

Ben@Rail will develop a top-down analysis grounded on two elements.

On the one side, the project will identify the requirements of the rail sector stakeholders vis a vis EU-funded research.

On the other side, the sector's strategic documents are reviewed and analysed in light of the stakeholders' expected benefits and the wider societal challenges to extract objectives, key technical concepts and development areas that will affect and shape the Railway System of the future.

The resulting analysis will assess the adherence of EU-funded R&I activities to the stakeholders' requirements, thus evaluating the expected outcomes of the future new Joint Undertaking Master Plan.

Ben@Rail will develop a scientific, innovative framework for the evaluation of EU-funded projects based on the stakeholders' requirements. One of the strengths of this framework relies on its possible application in other sectors to comprehensively investigate future funding R&I programmes.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Euronorm research and training programme 2019-2020) under grant agreement No. 101046258.

Figure 3. Ben@Rail digital flyer

6.2.4 Animated presentation

By the end of the project, an animated presentation or video will be produced to present the results of Ben@Rail (MS8, due in M9). The video will follow the communication guidelines of ERRAC Working Group 3 (communication) and presents the project results in a clear way targeting railway professionals as well as general public.

6.3 Dissemination events and participation in conferences

The Ben@Rail consortium will organise one main public event at the end of the project within the IMPACT-2 and Fine-2 final event. The Final Conference will be organised to present the major results of the project and raise awareness about Ben@Rail key conclusions. This conference will be open to anyone interested in participating. To ensure maximum impact, invitations will be sent to the key actors in the field.

Being it organised within the context of an event organised by IMPACT-2 and Fine-2, the location will be in Brussels and will take into consideration possible Covid-19 pandemic restrictions at the time of the event.

Apart from the final conference, Ben@Rail consortium will organise

- Targeted interviews to selected stakeholders with the objective to gather inputs on stakeholders' requirements;
- Two workshops with the objective to widen the audience for the RIA including stakeholders and stimulating the discussion on user requirements and benefits, held respectively within one ERRAC Steering Committee and one ERRAC Plenary.

All of the events will be organised with the collaboration of ERRAC.

Aside from these events, the project partners will be active in the project promotion and dissemination, by joining these and other major events and conferences and presenting results and achievements of the project.

6.4 Publication

Regular information shall be published through the usual channels of the partners involved in the project. Project results are also planned to be published through one article in Open Research Europe, Transport Research Arena (TRA2022, 14-17 November 2022 in Lisbon) or, additionally, in the ETR – Eisenbahntechnische Rundschau - Eurailpress.

Moreover, D4.3 "Summary of dissemination and exploitation activities", released in Month 9, will contain a detailed report on all the dissemination and exploitation activities performed within the project. D4.3 will be public and widely distributed by the Consortium members.

6.5 Social Network

Social networks are very efficient to target a large audience or more specific communities. The project social media presence aims at showing the progress and results of the project, widen the audience of Ben@Rail and improve the engagement with the stakeholders. To maximise the impacts of social media, Ben@Rail aims at liaising with Shift2Rail and relies on existing social media

profiles of the organisations involved, including Twitter and LinkedIn.

Twitter is one of the channels chosen for disseminating information about the project to a wide audience. The objective is to use the project coordinator existing Twitter account in order to leverage their already established audience when “tweeting” pieces of news such as news articles, information about Ben@Rail events, relevant conferences, major findings, etc.

One of the key advantages of using Twitter is that it enables the dissemination of short pieces of information which will contribute to driving back the traffic towards the project’s website. Another benefit is the multimedia support offered by Twitter, which allows partners to post short videos, text and pictures.

The partners will use the specific hashtag created for the project: #benatrail in order to maximise the impact of the outreach.

LinkedIn is the second social media employed for Ben@Rail dissemination strategy, as it allows to reach out to interested stakeholders who spend their professional working time on social media sites. In this context, the employment of LinkedIn allows the campaign to focus not only on the number of followers and interactions but on the quality and relevance of the people engaged.

7. Exploitation plan and knowledge transfer

7.1 Objectives

The objectives for the exploitation of results are the following:

- To ensure a good transfer of results between Ben@Rail and Shift2Rail.
- To ensure that Ben@Rail results will be forwarded through the dedicated initiatives in Shift2Rail future successor Europe's Rail.

7.2 Exploitation measures

To ensure the good transfer of results between Ben@Rail and Shift2Rail, the project will take the following steps:

- Develop and sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement for collaboration with the complementary CFM project IMPACT-2;
- Ensure a smooth transfer of Ben@Rail results to IMPACT-2, as well as with any other relevant future Europe's Rail project, through the organisation of technical workshops on specific subjects identified, whenever needed. These interactions will be managed on a case-by-case basis;
- Regular interaction with the S2R JU.

This exchange of information will enable the Ben@Rail project to provide feedback to Shift2Rail and its successor Europe's Rail.

7.3 Stakeholder engagement

Ben@Rail will ensure liaison and collaboration with Railway stakeholders within and outside ERRAC, the Shift2Rail JU, relevant ETPs, and the research community. Meetings will be organised to discuss strategical aspects, gather stakeholders' insights and assess the progress of the Ben@Rail project. To maximise the impact, these meetings will be jointly held with the ERRAC meeting sessions.

The dissemination and exploitation measures of the project will address the full range of potential users and uses. This includes Regulatory Bodies (ERA), Railway Undertakings, Associations (ERRAC), Freight Operators and Infrastructure Managers, Research centres, actors in the railway supply industry, Regional/National and European Institutions. The project will capitalise upon established contacts of the members networks and ways of working when trying to reach the most appropriate stakeholders to inform them on the project activities.

7.4 Close collaboration with and promotion of Shift2Rail JU

Ben@Rail will ensure close collaboration with Shift2Rail and will actively participate in liaising, dissemination, and communication activities promoted by Shift2Rail.

7.5 Collaboration with ERRAC

Cooperation with the ERRAC European Technology Platform (ETP) is extremely important to achieve Ben@Rail objectives. For this reason, the Consortium is engaged in ERRAC activities, and the project events will be held within ERRAC meetings, as mentioned in section 7.3.

7.6 Collaboration with IMPACT-2

A special attention will be put in the collaboration with Shift2Rail project S2R-CFM-CCA-01-2017 (IMPACT-2) to learn from each other's results and develop a streamlined and efficient work flow. The consortium leader of the IMPACT-2 was invited to the Ben@Rail kick-off meeting and presented ideas to foster collaboration between the two projects.

A teleconference between Ben@Rail and IMPACT-2 will be organised before Month 3 to share views on both projects and specific insights on their relationship.

Moreover, Ben@Rail final conference will be held within the IMPACT-2 and Fine-2 final event, ensuring collaboration between the projects.

7.7 Knowledge transfer

The final document (D3.1) released in Month 9 “Top-down analysis of the railway stakeholders’ masterplan goals” will ensure effective transfer of knowledge between Ben@Rail and the Shift2Rail JU.

The analysis will identify both concepts that are met by stakeholders’ expectations as well as concepts which might be further developed to improve the adherence between the stakeholders’ expectations and the ERJU Master Plan. D3.1 will contribute to S2R expected results by contributing to align the R&I activities with the user needs; quantifying the users benefits by considering the future sustainable multi-modal door to door services; contributing as far as possible to any future realignment of the rail R&I priorities and scope. This analysis can then be used to form recommendations for actions for the new Joint Undertaking Master Plan.

8. Conclusions

This document provides plans in the areas of dissemination, exploitation and knowledge transfer. It presents a comprehensive dissemination strategy for the Ben@Rail project and describes the materials and strategies that have been and will be used for external communication, along with the engagement and uptake of the results by relevant stakeholders.

The participation to a series of dissemination events has been planned, however, it is anticipated that more dissemination opportunities will arise as the project progresses. Therefore, the Ben@Rail consortium will use this plan as an initial strategy which will be further updated and reviewed. Dissemination activities will be discussed at WP level and will be coordinated generally via WP4. Routes to exploitation have been identified and the specific cooperation with the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking, ERRAC and the relevant CCA project will be a key activity to ensure success to all the entities involved.

The results of the activities of this work package and the impact of Ben@Rail will be monitored by the project coordinator, EURNEX.